

Creating fiscal space for health in 30 low- and middle-income countries

Policy Brief

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About this Policy Brief

This policy brief was developed as part of the collaboration between the Harvard Health Systems Innovation Lab and the *Changing Diabetes in Children (CDiC)* program, in collaboration with and supported by Novo Nordisk. The analysis currently focuses on the 30 countries where CDiC is active. The brief presents results on opportunities to expand fiscal space for health. A technical report and manuscript with detailed methodology and findings are forthcoming.

Why fiscal space matters

Low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) are facing constrained resource envelopes for funding essential health service delivery. For CDiC countries, this means less funding available to finance the delivery of type 1 diabetes (T1D) services. However, there is also an opportunity for domestic government resources to sustainably fill this gap in funding. **In this brief, we estimate how much fiscal space for health can reasonably be mobilized under alternative policy pathways.**

What we did

We modeled four scenarios for 2025–2030 using internationally comparable macro-fiscal data for 30 CDiC countries.

Modeled scenarios include:

- **Macroeconomic growth:** Additional fiscal space generated if economies grow and health maintains its current share of GDP.
- **Budget reprioritization:** Increased allocation of government resources to health, converging toward best-performing peers.
- **Health taxes:** Higher excise taxes on tobacco, alcohol, and sugar-sweetened beverages.
- **Loans:** Expanded borrowing for health investment based on peer benchmarks.

We estimate additional government fiscal space for health reported as total USD, per-capita USD, and relative change (%) compared to 2022 government health spending levels.

What we found

Budget reprioritization and macroeconomic growth drive most gains.

- A total of **3.1 trillion USD** could be mobilized through 2030 (Figure 1).
- Across CDiC countries, most of the potential fiscal space by 2030 comes from increased health prioritization and macroeconomic growth.
- Taxes and loans generate comparatively small potential gains.

Per-capita gains rise with income level.

- Upper-middle-income countries could mobilize substantially larger per-capita resources than low-income countries (Figure 2).
- Structural economic differences limit gains in lower-income settings.

Figure 1. Total fiscal space for health, 2025 – 2030.

Figure 2. Per-capita gains in fiscal space in 2030.

Country variation is wide.

- Country-level impacts vary widely, from small gains (e.g., Mozambique, Rwanda), to negative changes in some settings (e.g., Nigeria), to very large gains in others (e.g., Guinea, Cameroon) (Figure 3).
- Large economies dominate total additional fiscal space mobilized.

Figure 3. Country-specific average relative change (%) in fiscal space, 2025 – 2030.

Figure 3 Note: Bangladesh is excluded from this figure to improve visual scale. Full results in forthcoming technical report/manuscript.

What this means

- Domestic fiscal space expansion is feasible in many CDiC countries.
- Most additional resources would come from broader fiscal prioritization rather than new earmarked taxes.
- Health taxes and borrowing can supplement but are unlikely to close financing gaps alone.
- Lower-income countries will generate smaller absolute gains even under optimistic scenarios.
- Translating fiscal space into financing for T1D specifically will require deliberate allocation decisions.

